

Department of Research and Developments

Odeonus LLC

United States of America.

www.odeonus.com

researches@odeonus.com

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National, Financial and Political Rise and falls of Pakistan

In the developments of any nation or a country is their consistent and continuous struggle in a controlled manners. The statistical analysis which made any nation or organization successful.

Consistency and Analytics are the two factors by which an individual or an organization can get their direction controlled and the continuity proves the work.

National downfall:

The main reason of the downfall of the country is unmaintained only initiative attitude. In the last many decades the nation of Pakistan had been suffering by that kind of attitude. It is not an individual's attitude but of the whole nation.

Political downfall:

In the same manners the politics of Pakistan had been suffering. One more reason of the falls of Pakistan is interior political mess. Absence of national political decisions. Political superiority over other political parties becoming the reason of national political down fall.

Financial downfall:

Financial downfall of the country is affected by the same attitude. Business and financial institutions' lake of statistical control on need variation and initiative only behavior downed the organizations or a country.

When you lose the high opportunities:

Mr. Atta-ur-Rahman: We, Odeonus LLC, would try to put your intention on the personality who is Mr. Atta-ur-Rahman.

Prof. Dr. Atta-ur-Rahman is the most sophisticated scientist of Pakistan. He has been serving between 14th March, 2000 – 20th November, 2002 as a Federal Minister for Science and Technology, in 2002 Federal Minister of Education and Higher Education Commission's Chairman from 2002-2008 with the status of a Federal Minister. ⁽¹⁾

Lost the opportunity:

As a federal minister of science and technology and higher education he defined the new ways to lift up the falls of the nation by the advanced education and technologies. But the inconsistency, un-control and absence of maintainability become the reason of fall of the practices.

Graphical representation of the reasons of downfall: a solution.

The absolute point of efforts we would try to show in the following graph.

Graph of Stability

- Green area representing the absolute progress
- Red area representing the uncontrolled progress
- Red bars are representing the absolute points of stability

You can see in the graph the variation of process appeared outside of the red bars of the absolute points of stability appearing the absence of consistency and control.

Consistency and Control: These two factors directly affects the progress of any work. Whether you struggle in education, financials, politics, social, religious, power,

ethical, national, international or in any aspects of life you need constant and controlled struggle to get succeeded.

In Pakistan the reason of instability: in every aspect of life the absence of Continuity, consistency and control is the reason of instability. It is what Pakistan or any organization or a country need to be get succeeded.

Modern Technologies: like **Mind-reader** or **Brain Computer Interface (BCI)**, **Electroencephalograms (EEGs)**, **Electrocardiograms (ECGs)**, **Bone Conductor (BC)** or **Voice-to-Skull (V2K)** can help in providing control over the consistent struggle.

Reference Links:

⁽¹⁾ <https://www.interacademies.org/person/atta-ur-rahman>
<https://atta-ur-rahman.com/?page=home>
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Atta-ur-Rahman_\(chemist\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Atta-ur-Rahman_(chemist))